

the date given by Turnour, while the editors of the second part of the Mah. have put 1745 instead.

157. Pillar of Lag Wijaya Singa Kit, found on the bund of Abhayawaewa tank at Anurādhapura, now in the Colombo Museum. The inscriber is the same Lag Wijaya Singa mentioned in No. 156, but here he calls himself chief minister to Līlavatī's, royal consort Abhā Salamewan. Now, from the Mah. (80, 30, 31) we know only of a General Kīrtisena, who married Parākramabāhu's widow Līlavatī and reigned three years (1797–1200) after which time he was deposed by Sāhasa Malla. It is unlikely, although not impossible, that Lag Wijaya Singa should have been first the minister of Kirtisena and then have installed his enemy, Sāhasa Malla. Līlavatī was restored twice to the throne by the Tamils in 1209 for one year, and in 1211 for seven months only, but nowhere in the Mah. she is connected with a prince of the name of Abhaya Salamewan, so this must remain undecided for the present. The inscription contains a grant to the priests living in the Ruwanpāya, and resembles also in the language very much the pillar inscriptions of the 10th and 11th centuries.

Following the chronological order, we have to mention now two inscriptions of a king who calls himself Siri Sanga bo Parākramabāhu. One of them (158) is on the pavement of the southern altar of the Ruanwaeli Dāgoba, the other one (159) was found at Dondra,* near Matara (S.P.), and is now in the Colombo Museum. The latter was published by T. W. Rhys Davids first in the *Indian Antiquary*, I. 619, and afterwards in the *J. C. A. S.* 1871–72, p. 57, but he ascribed it to Sulu Siri Sanga bo (712–718 A.D.) In the proceedings, however, p. XXIV., he states, that the chief interest of the inscription lies in the simultaneous gift to Hindu and Buddhist temples, showing that as at the present day so in the year A.D. 1400, Buddhism was corrupted with Hindu rites, &c. As we have seen in the pillar inscriptions of the 10th and 11th centuries, the Sinhalese kings often call themselves by other names than those given in the Mahāvansa, and we have, therefore, to take into consideration chiefly the language and the contents of the inscriptions. The language of the Dondra inscription is evidently more modern, not only than that of the pillars, but also than that of Niçṣaṅka Malla; as for the subjects, it is a dedication of cocoanut trees to the temple of Wishṇu at Dondra, and therefore does not prove anything for the date of the inscription. In fact, it would be difficult to make out the age of this stone if the name of the king and the language did not agree so well with the other inscription at the Ruanwaeli Dāgoba. This latter is not mentioned in any book, and seems to have been quite unknown to the present. It begins with Abhaya Salamewan, and then follows at the end of the first line the name of the King Siri Sangabo Parākramabāhu; besides these there are mentioned in

* *Comp. Forbes II.*, 178.

the third line one Wijaya and his mother Sumedhā. The contents of the inscription are religious; the king relates how he worshipped the Ruanwaeli Dāgoba, how he spent five yālas of rice, a large ocean of milk, and 2,000 kalandas of incense, how he recompensed the working people and their mothers with gold and clothes, how he listened to the Thūpawansa, and worshipped the Thūpārāma and the sacred Botree, &c. Among the kings that can come into consideration there is only Wijayabāhu II., who was a zealous Buddhist; the story of his reign is thus introduced in the Mah. 81, 10:

Tadā khalu Siri sangha bodhi rājanvayāgato rājā Vijaya bāhu ti vissuto cāruvikkamo. So there is no doubt about his name being Siri Sanghabo; his relationship is not given in the Mah., but he claimed descentance from the unfortunate Siri Sanghabo I. (246-248), a martyr of the Buddhist faith. As Mr. Davids pointed out in the passage already quoted, it is no matter of surprise to see that a king who professes to be a zealous Buddhist at the same time bestows gifts upon a Hindu temple, as in the 13th century Buddhism had adopted the cult of Wishṇu and other Hindu deities. The temple at Dondra to which the inscription refers is a Buddhist temple now, but there are still to be seen the statues of Wishṇu, Gaṇeṣa, and the sacred bull of Tanjore, which evidently do not at all interfere with the Buddhistical worship.

160. Inscription at the Paepiliyāna temple near Koṭṭa. This is a grant by the first King of Koṭṭa Parākramabāhu VI., made in the 39th year of his reign. As the date of his accession is given the year 1958 A.B., which agrees with that given in the foot note to p. XXII. of the list prefixed to the second part of the Mahāvansa. The stone which contained the inscription is broken now, and the pieces have been used for the construction of the outer wall of the Paepiliyāna* temple at the junction of the two roads from Pamankanda to Horana, and from Koṭṭa to Galkissa. The priest, however, has got a copy which I used for making the transcript, after having compared it with the fragments. A part of it has been published with a translation by James Alwis in the introduction to the Sidat Sangarāwa, p. CXCIX.

161. Inscription at the Gane wihāra near Waeligāma (S. P.) published by T. W. Rhys Davids in the J. C. A. S. 1870-71, p. 21. the king calls himself Siri Sanghabo Siri Bhuwaneka bāhu, and is most probably the sixth of his name who reigned from 1464 to 1471.

162. Inscription at Kaelani (see No. 127) published by L. de Zoysa Mahāmudaliyar in the J. C. A. S. 1871-72, p. 36; this is on a stone slab near the ancient Kaelani temple, on the left shore of the Kaelani gangā while the new one is on the right. It records an account of the repairs executed in this temple by King Dharma Parākramabāhu of Koṭṭa who

* This temple is mentioned in the Parawi sandesa, a poem by Ćri Rāhula of Toṭagamūwa stanza 46.

wannē Anurādhapurehi paṭan bhūmiye taman kaeraewū ruwan pāyehi waedaē hun saūgu

B.—ruwanṭa siwu pasayen wana pāsu piṇisae tamanṭa bat giṇuwa yaewin yālak hā mehi mae caityayaṭa yālak hā piḷimageṭa yālak hā bhūmi dāna koṭae hira sandapamaṇa wae pidū pāsāyēn pirinaemū me lābhaya antarāya kaḷawun

C.—windinā narakādi duk daen hā matu matu wanā nuwanaetiyan lobha dwesha māna duru koṭae lābha antarāya no koṭae nuwanaettan kaḷa anumowanu maenaewi.

158. Inscription at the southern Altar, Ruanwaeli Dāgoba, Anurādhapura :—

(1.) Abhayae Salamēwan kala raṇa wala suwāmin wahanse pra dewanu Aesaḷa pura ekoḷos wak tin Siri saūga bo Prākramabāhū

(2.) cakkrawartti suwāmin wānsē aetuḷuwū raja daruwangē bhaṇḍāra paripālanaya koṭa ratnatrayehi adhikaprapāḷa aeti ṇa busagūṇe

(3.) n sama citarājapa prasādarāsīn wirājamāna wū bhaṇḍāra potae piriwatu bim Wijayayānna wannā mekuḡē am wū Sume

(4.) dhā dewinhā mekuḡe baen Laūkā adhikāra koṭa danaṭa dewal nā panha tun denae āga wisarata ek

(5.) paso tawarayangen Ruwanmaeli suwāmīṇṭa Duṭugae-muṇu rajjuruwan ādi wū no ek

(6.) rajadaruwan wisin karana lada pūjā wiṇesha aṇā prasāda parawaṇawa anun hā asādhārana pū

(7.) jā wiṇeshayak kaḷa maenaewaeyi nānāwidhawū aṭa dās aṭa siyā asūwak pamaṇa wastrayen wiṇe

(8.) sha wū koṭu kayak webāwūyā maṇi caitya pratibimbayak se wiṇesha koṭa sarahā pas yālak pa

(9.) maṇa sālin soḷos mahalā andawā gandhapushpa sugandha payen wicitra koṭae pānō ge

(10.) nae dhaja patāka kadaḷi toraṇādīn wiḷi sarahā aneka awaggayeka na daeyin hā kshīrapāyāsa

(11.) yen hā mahodhayak se paḷamuwana maḷuwehi niran-tarayen satiyak pūjā koṭae kapura de dāsak

(12.) kaḷandin pātae tunwana piya wadā we riyanā riyanē kawel waḷae kapuru pān pudā ae

(13.) gāe aetuḷu wū no ek wastu pradīpa wū pūjā da karawā no ek kammānta kaḷa mehe kara

(14.) wanṭa atāṭa gal ebū mundu hā ran piḷi hā un ambu-wanṭa da handanā piḷi di un dā satuṭu karawā

(15.) wihā (?) rakshā we siṭi liyannawūn samadaruwan waṇ-ṇatuwarun bamunan pasakun sittarun

(16.) nawannan gikiyannan beragasannan sakun jarasan padāyan paweniye paṇi nahana gāe

(17.) nun dāmā le baelū maṅgul miṇḍiyan mālakā tin osanā waṭuwan waḷā jayen ranin sa

(18.) tuṭu karawā Ruwanmaeli maḷuwe di me Thūpawamṇa asā dhamma kathikayanṭa sudusu pūjāwā koṭa du

(19.) thūpārāma swāmīṇṭat ṇri mahā bodhinwabansetṭat ka-wuru pahan patā kāpu hā āwiwu no ek

(20.) pūjā karawā sat geṇehi terawarun wahanse prasanna koṭae wahnātāt at mangadan . . . wu

(21.) rū pīlī dī nāe no nāe ne siyalu pritayan wapin pat duwāre pūjā aesū mahājanayāta data māta da

(22.) bahalapriti upadawā kalawū.

159. Dondra I. :—Siri saṅga bo ḡri Parākramabāhu cakrawartti swāminwahansēta 10 warusha tinen bhūmi mahā wihārayāta acrae tumbu ranata gatu aetikala pol wattayi pilimagēta gas 200 yi Dew rajjuru sāmiṅta warddhana kaḡawuge taeyi me lesae mekuṅge paramparāwen pawat wāsaga mok sampat saediya yutu me gasa prayojana windinawun matu matun paela induwa yutuyi minissu . . . ntan mehi prayojana ekkoṭae nīla saclasiya yutu.

160. Paepiliyāna wihāra.—ḡri Lamkādhpatiḡ Parākramabhujas sūryyānvayālamkṛitir yyācehambhavato vacaḡ ḡriṅnuta me bhūmiḡvarā bhavinā dharmmo yaṃ sadṛiḡaḡ samastajagatā satyaṃ bhavadbhiḡ sadā rakshyo sau me jātahasahā kṛipayā puṅyan tathā bhujyatām.

ḡri Lamkādhpatiḡ Parākramabhujō rājā wihārottamaṃ svaprasvākyamakārasajjagadiyantrāṅa satasyādhunā sadaḡrāmānvidhān pradāya sajanānārāmavāpyāḡrayān saṃsādhin nayācirāya tanute sthānaṃ ḡilāḡāsanam.

ḡri Buddhawarshayen ek dahas nawa siya aṡa panas awurudak piruṅu sada siri Lakaraja paemini mahāsammata paramparānuyāta sūryyawamḡabhijāta mahārajādhirāja ḡri Saṃghabodhi ḡri Parākramabāhu cakrawartti swāmin wahanseṡta ekunsāliswanu Maendindina pura pasaloṡwak jayawarddhana puraprawarayehi Sumaṅgala prasādābhimukha citra maṅḡa payehi siṃhāsanaṡyehi siri niwes saha bhaṡunu siwiḡuṡabaraṅin ḡaedi raja yuwaraja aemati gaṅa piriwarā dewindra lilāwen waḡa hinda haema tanhi kaḡa manā kaṡayuttāta waewasthā wadāraṅa taena swarggastha wū mawubisawun wahanseṡta pin pinisa abhinawa wihārayak karawaṅa lesaṡa rāṅiwāsalakāriyehi niyukta sikurā mudal pokunaṡa wadāḡa mehewarin pas wisi dahasak dhana wiyadan koṡa pānabunu bada paepiliyānehi prakāra gōpura pratimā grahamāṅḡapa bodhimainya saṃghāwāsa dewāla satraya pustakālaya pushpārāma phalārāmādin yukta koṡa samurdha karawū wihāraya cirasthāyi warddhana wana pinisa piduyen me ma paepiliyāna hā mehi bada maedi māla hā amutu wa dimbul piṡiyen piduyen wēllen uḡa deniyen dasa amuṅak hā katthatoṡa badden akē goḡawila hā mehi bada wal piṡawatu paelaen aetuḡu wū taen hā pas yodun

161. Waeligāma wihāra.—(1) Siri saṅga bo (2) ḡri Bhuwa naikabā (3) hu cakrawartti swāmi (4) n wahanseṡta sawana hawurudu (5) kaḡu Parākrama nam mantriḡwara (6) yā mehe karuwanta kuli dī kaerae (7) wū me saṃghikisak so pirimasā (8) sasae hindinā denamakata niran (9) [ta] ra pasayan dī satara digin waḡa (10) nā saṃghayā wahanseṡtat dawa (11) sak pasaya dena lesaṡa ramṅaṡa ge (12) lawa kumburu mal bijuwāta da sāmu (13) da . . . pala da polwattat wahal (14) pas denan sarak yālat

(him) with splendour becoming the future dignity of royalty, having overthrown in two years the bad counsellors, who, having heard this thing, not liking kings who powerful both for reward and punishment would protect world and religion, desiring each their own government, made obstacles, shining like the full moon when she has risen under a lucky constellation, seeking their way on the ocean, without obstacles, having come, having united Trisimhala under one umbrella, when 1743 years three months 27 days had gone since Buddha on the 12th in the bright half of Binera, on Tuesday, having been crowned under a lucky constellation, having for this service, unequalled by others, invested him with the rang of a general, and thinking : To mothers who have got such children it is right to give superlative honour, having given the name Lamkātilakamahādewī to their mother, having girded her with a golden girdle, having given much honour, (thinking) it is right that to all the fortune with villages and retinue which I have given to General Lag Wijaya Singa having made it last as long as sun and moon exist, future princes also (shall stick) because it is a duty of the kings to protect those who to every one do a service, not making obstruction, having it established in this way, shall protect their family, he was pleased to put up an inscription. If seeing this king's friends, ministers, etc., should take by violence this said property they will become like low caste man, crows and dogs. Therefore such people as wish to protect loyalty, shall protect all the property given to these.

King Sāhasa Malla revered in the world prays himself as protection of stout adherents, is the first law for kings, therefore, may the kings protect the family of the aged general who caused the ascendancy of the Kālinga family together with the fortune.

157. Pillar of Lag Wijaya Singu Kit.—“General Lag Wijaya-siṅgu Kit, chief minister to Lilāvati's royal consort, Abhā Salamewan, who comes from the royal race of the glorious Ikshwāku family—in the third year (of the king's reign) having made a donation of land: one yāḷa for rice barley (?) to the priests themselves living in the Ruwanpāya (ratnaprasāda, ‘palace of jewels’) which he himself built on ground from Anurādhapura, for their ease that it may serve for the four pratyaya's, and one yāḷa to the caitya here and one yāḷa to the image-house—the pain in hell, which those shall suffer who obstruct this merit acquired from the offered which shall last as long as sun and moon endure (literally: ‘sun and moon being the measure’), shall be now and in all future, (but) wise men who, having renounced covetousness, hatred, pride, and not obstructing the merit, do may be pleased to share (the merit).”

158. Ruanwaeli Dāgoba, pavement Southern Altar.—.
Abhaya Salamewan the lord in the eleventh
day in the second half of Aesaḷa His Majesty Siri
sangabo Parākramabāhu cakrawartī the lord including the

princes protecting with the three gems
 resplendent the heap of prosperity in the bhaṇḍāra book
 surrounding the earth Wijaya and his mother Sumedhā,
 the goddess, and having made their brother lord of Laṅkā for
 giving things three people beginning
 with the King Duṭugaemuṇu, lord of the Ruanwæli having
 heard of the exquisite honour done to it by many princes he was
 pleased to favour in an extraordinary way in
 different manners 8880 measures, by (giving) clothes
 having made an image of the caitya and having decorated
 it five yālas of rice, sixteen having
 decorated it with sweet smelling flowers, having adorned it with
 flags, banners, and arches, having offered, without interruption, a
 hundred garlands like the great ocean two
 thousand kaḷandas of camphor, having offered from cubit to
 cubit kaluwael and camphor incense, including this, having
 offered many lamps, having given to the working people that did
 much work gold (?) clothes and to their wives
 clothes for wearing, and having made them satisfied, having . . .
 to the writers staying in the wihāra, to the
 the brahmans, the pasakas, the painters, the goldsmiths, the
 musicians, the tom tom beaters, the
 servants of the feast garlands having made
 them satisfied with gold, having given it to the terrace of the
 Ruanwæli, having heard the Thūpawaṃṇa, having saluted
 those who recited the dhamma, having offered incense to the
 Thūpārāma and to the sacred bo-tree, having made the theras
 propitious by seven gaṇas (?)

159. Dondra I.—In the 10th year of His Majesty Siri Sanga
 Bo Parākramabāhu a cocoanut tope bought for a tumba (?) of
 gold to the Bhūmi mahā wihāra and to the image house, and
 200 cocoanut trees to the Lord Dewarāja. Let those who increase
 these gifts and uphold their continual inheritance, enjoy the bliss
 of release in heaven. Those who enjoy the fruit of these trees
 ought, from time to time, to plant seedlings. People
 who join into the same purpose should hold office.

160. Paepiliyāna wihāra.—Parākramabhūja, the lord of Laṅkā,
 the ornament of the family of the sun (says): I ask you, hear
 my word, the word of a future lord of the world (?). This law
 similar in the whole world is to be kept by you; this, the reason
 of my happiness, may produce the good in a merciful mind (?).

Parākramabhūja, the lord of Laṅkā, erects the celebrated
 wihāra called by his name having given to the
 pious people tanks and gardens and lodgings [and records this
 fact] by a stone-inscription.

In the year of Buddha one thousand nine hundred and fifty-
 eight, in the 39th year of the great king Ćrī Saṃghabodhi Ćrī
 Parākramabāhu, born of the Solar race, and a descendant of
 King Mahāsammata on the 15th day in the bright half of Maen-
 dindina, in the chief city of Jayawardhana, on his throne which